

Part III: Presentation of Selected Authors and their Texts

For background's sake, I will provide a general overview of the two selected Francophone African authors and their respective selected texts, whose styles serve as a case study in the present research, relying on prior studies. An African novel is a work authored by an African, whether in the diaspora or present on the continent, and deals with questions and subject matters relating to the continent and/or the "living conditions and life of Africans" across/beyond the borders (Tanyitiku 4). Francophone African novelists take the liberty of what Damola Adeyefa calls the stylistic eccentricity in their novels to portray the indigenous image and the traditional riches of their land ("Translation" 67). The notion of eccentricity here cuts across the creative freedom exercised by the writer to reveal specific African cultural uniqueness. They connect their experience, history, and identity to their literary writing.

a) Mariama Bâ

Mariama Bâ is known as a prominent author with distinction. She is classified among "the first generation of female Senegalese" authors (Azado 422); and through the narrative style and the themes of her novels, she has earned a prestigious position for herself in literary discourse (Deokate and Cherekar 124).

One of the crucial experiences capable of shaping Mariama Bâ's inspiration in writing is the death of her mother while Mariama Bâ was still very young. Moving into the house of her grandparents, where she was eventually brought up, adds another experience to her existence (Hamidouche 60). Born in 1929, her early life was spent under the colonial administration in Senegal (Swoboda 143). Religion and the Koranic school were part of the growing forces in the community where Mariama Bâ grew up. And thus, she has more than enough to write about these themes. Her formal education in the 1930s was a result of her strong determination to step out of

the existing norm of the society where only the masculine gender is encouraged for such education: neither the grandparents nor the Senegalese community of that epoch believed in the significance of education to a girl (Amissine 16), since theologians' discourse in the country was disputing the right of the feminine gender to school (Hamidouche 60).

Mariama Bâ gave herself to personal development and excellence, as evident in her brilliant performance in school. This quest for excellence is woven into her authorial style. A set of experiences finds its way into Mariama Bâ's works: marriages and divorces. She had the experience of living with three consecutive husbands as a result of divorce. After all, her ambition was to ensure the education of her offspring, the sustenance of her career, and her writing. She birthed new dreams and was ready to champion a civilized movement for the improvement of the feminine life, especially in Africa, working in many feminist associations. It is equally worth mentioning that Mariama Bâ also experienced wealth. As a member of the rich elites, her grandfather, as well as other men of her large family, had, at a certain time, assumed renowned positions in Senegalese society (Hamidouche 60).

b) Une si longue lettre

Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre* (an object of my analysis), remains one of the significant novels in the literary world. It received, according to Hudson (Weems), the "first African publishers" Noma Award (63). Mariama Bâ's interest lies in criticizing the life of African women in relation to colonialism, civilization, and religion (Deokate and Cherekar 124). Uzoamaka Azodo argues that her intended audience is everyone everywhere, and her works portray both men and women in general with no "discrimination to race and creed" (422).

The life of Mariama Bâ can be studied throughout the novel. Published before she died in 1981, Anna Swoboda argues that *Une si longue lettre* is a "semi-autobiographical and an epistolary

novel,” as conveyed in the title of the work. In the text, Aissatou Bâ is the addressee of the long letter being written by her friend Ramatoulaye Fall. Both characters were born under colonial rule in Senegal, attended school together, and grew up after the country’s independence. Their lives were shaped by both tradition and Western civilization (143). Therefore, the novelist’s life is an integral part of the study of *Une si longue lettre* (Amissine 16). Both her childhood, education, adulthood, marriages, and social activities enormously inform her writing and stylistic eccentricity.

Une si longue lettre is widely accepted in many languages across the world. The account of Tobias Warner reveals that, shortly after its first publication in 1979, this popular text was already published “in more than half a dozen translations, including English” (1239). This number grew, and the novel is now “translated into over seventeen different languages and adapted into stage plays and television films in Wolof” (Ndiaye 178–180).

Though less (biographical) information is available on the translator, Felix Faniran (among others) acknowledges Modupe Bode-Thomas’ excellent work of making this novel available for the English-speaking community (189). The original author, Mariama Bâ, and her English translator Modupe Bode-Thomas have some things in common, according to the account of Adeboye Gbadegesin and Oremeyi Shaibu, though both writers are from different African countries. Like Mariama Bâ, the translator is a teacher at The Polytechnic, Ibadan, Nigeria. Both women have a common sociocultural experience as Africans (289). Therefore, I recognize the translator’s closeness to Mariama Bâ’s life and culture.

The content includes psychic issues surrounding Ramatoulaye’s marriage with Modou Fall, when the thirty-year-old home transitions into polygamy. Among the central themes of this Francophone African novel is “the life of women in the patriarchal society in Africa” (Deokate and Cherekar 125). Such a life is like Mariama Bâ’s, as she wrote this roman “through the eye of

her first-person narrator, Ramatoulaye, who writes a long letter to her childhood friend, Aissatou” (Amissine 55), who resides in America. The content of the letter is the novel itself, as the text opens with the salutation, “Aissatou” (Bâ, *Une si longue lettre* 7).

One of the protagonist’s aims in writing the letter is to update her recipient on her experience. She is obligated by the Islamic tradition to stay in seclusion for a certain number of days as a result of Modou Fall’s sudden death. Ramatoulaye also uses the letter as a means of relieving herself of the mental “burdens she has to cope” with in the new phase of her life, as she recalls not only the events of Modou Fall’s death but also her experience and that of her friend, Aissatou (Amissine 55).

Aissatou is a perfect recipient of such a long letter because she has a similar life. The marriage of the protagonist with Modou Fall has a wonderful beginning, like Aissatou’s marriage with Mawdo Ba. The respective in-laws of both friends subjugate them, and both homes were broken by polygamy. According to African societal norms, Ramatoulaye and Aissatou should still maintain their faithfulness and commitment to their respective husbands till death separates the couple, even if the wife is abandoned, neglected, or maltreated by the men (56).

Aissatou’s decision that differs from her friend’s is the immediate step she takes to divorce her husband, Mawdo Ba, when he marries a second wife, Nabou. After this divorce, Aissatou proceeds to obtain her degree in diplomacy, which eventually allows her to take a role in the Senegalese embassy in America. Ramatoulaye remains loyal and dutiful to Modou Fall, even after he marries Binetou as a second wife. Ramatoulaye probably believes that he would care for her children. But Modou Fall’s death left Ramatoulaye as the only person to bring her children up.

Another difference between the friends is the respective social classes of their husbands: Aissatou belongs to a goldsmith father but married Mawdo Ba, the medical doctor, even at the

expense of her mother-in-law's disapproval. Ramatoulaye, on the other hand, is more educated than Modou Fall. However, she agrees to marry him over her family's objection. Throughout her *Une si longue lettre*, Mariama Bâ weaves the various themes strategically through her distinctive style as an African author.

c) **Cheikh Kane**

The second Francophone African novelist of interest in the present study is Hamadou Cheikh Kane. Just like Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre*, studies reveal that *L'Aventure ambiguë* reflects some personal experiences of Cheikh Kane. Moreover, the author himself (Cheikh Kane) confirmed this to Janet Patricia Little in an interview. His childhood was influenced by his relatives. It was in 1928, in the Djallobé country, that Cheikh Kane was born to a "traditional Toucouleur family" whose patriarch (known as Alpha Ciré Diallo) hailed from Yirlabe province and came to settle in St. Louis (Senegal) in the nineteenth century (Ba-Curry 112). It was through this region that the Islamic religion invaded Africa in the eleventh century.

Therefore, Cheikh Kane grew up in a religious civilization, just like the character of Samba Diallo in the novel. At the age of ten, he got enrolled in a French school where he encountered French language. Before then, Peuhl was his only language. One of his childhood preoccupations was the recitation of the Koranic verses, and this made its way into his texts (Kane et al. 3). After his Koranic school, Cheikh Kane studied French in Dakar and then went for his law studies in France. After his studies, he rose to prominence in the Senegalese nation.

d) **L'aventure Ambiguë**

Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* is another well-recognized Francophone African text. The author began to write it from the year 1952 until it was finally published in 1961 (Mohamed 600). Like Mariama Bâ's *Une si longue lettre*, Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* is known as

“one of the most widely read novels in African literature in French” (Correa 83) and won the award of “Le Grand Prix Littéraire d’Afrique noire d’expression française 1962” after its publication in 1961 with Julliard (Kane et al. 5).

Later, Katherine Woods translated *L’Aventure ambiguë* as *Ambiguous Adventure* (1963). Like Modupe Bode-Thomas of *So Long A Letter*, little is known of Katherine Woods’ background vis-a-vis *Ambiguous Adventure*. However, I am holding the claim that the translator’s acquaintance with the source author’s ecologies is, doubtlessly, necessary to detect the right context and perspectives defining the source in units and as a whole.

Right from the beginning of the novel, Paris is on the other side, and the author’s birthplace is in Senegal, in a village whose name is represented by “L.” The author, through the main character, Samba Diallo, compares his mystic religious experience in his native country with that of science or civilization (Kane et al. 3–4). The people he grew up with, his Koranic studies, his formal education, his travels, and his civil service (among others) impact his writing and stylistic idiosyncrasies.

The novelist indirectly narrates the features of his personal life, including the internal and external factors that influence him and the time of his existence. The origin of the ambiguity in the text is the coincidence of the author’s observation of facts and the philosophical interpretation he gives to these observed facts (Kane et al. 4). Prior research also holds a claim that ambiguity is evidently present in the way the novelist characterizes the African cultures from a postcolonial perspective.

Cheikh Kane’s *L’Aventure ambiguë* describes the Cheikh Kane’s escapades embedded in “the existential philosophy of the protagonist, Samba Diallo” (Chigbu et al. 118). From a religious point of view, scholars note that this text seems to be “the first major work of African fiction to

construct an explicit defense of African Islamic life and faith against the European ideological and cultural menace.” The language and the themes that make up this classical novel, as posited by Cherif Correa, attract readership from all African secondary schools and universities (83) for being one of the great fictions known all over the world (Mohamed 600). This text has been added to the curriculum of the Senegalese system of education, thereby making it available to most Francophone students to encounter it, accordingly (Correa 83).

In a sociopolitical context, the novel was published shortly after Senegal’s freedom from the French administration. The text represents more than a mere celebration of African independence: the post-independence issues faced by the African society are clearly documented in the narrative. Through this novel, Cheikh Kane invites the world to consider the advantages and the disadvantages of “independence in novel terms” (Correa 83). In addition, the text reveals the “growth stance of Diallobé” as a nation reacting to Western education and civilization (Chigbu et al. 118).

In the text, the protagonist, Samba Diallo, from the Diallobé folks in Senegal, receives a Koranic education under the supervision of Thierno. As a young child, the protagonist hardly understands many lessons he is taught from the sacred book, though he is devoted to memorizing and reciting the verses. The Diallobé people eventually decide to enroll him in the French school. This could be an attempt to learn the Western culture so that the Diallobé can adjust to the spreading civilization around the world of the time.

Unfortunately, delving into this Western culture and civilization through education does not achieve Diallobé’s initial goal. Through his philosophy studies, Samba Diallo is gradually separated from his religion and his Diallobé culture. This presents the ambiguous adventure of

Samba Diallo, leaving his identity in-between his roots and the West, and the struggle is how to reconcile both worlds.

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